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BIG DATA IN CLOUD COMPUTING REVIEW AND OPPORTUNITIES

**Manoj Muniswamaiah, Tilak Agerwala and Charles Tappert
Seidenberg School of CSIS, Pace University, White Plains, New York**

ABSTRACT

Big Data is used in decision making process to gain useful insights hidden in the data for business and engineering. At the same time it presents challenges in processing, cloud computing has helped in advancement of big data by providing computational, networking and storage capacity. This paper presents the review, opportunities and challenges of transforming big data using cloud computing resources.

KEYWORDS

Big data; cloud computing; analytics; database; data warehouse

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SMART MOTORCYCLE HELMET: REAL-TIME CRASH DETECTION WITH EMERGENCY NOTIFICATION, TRACKER AND ANTI-THEFT SYSTEM USING INTERNET-OF-THINGS CLOUD BASED TECHNOLOGY

Marlon Intal Tayag¹ and Maria Emmalyn Asuncion De Vigal Capuno²

¹College of Information and Communications Technology Holy Angel University,
Angeles, Philippines

²Faculty of Information Technology Future University, Khartoum, Sudan

ABSTRACT

Buying a car entails a cost, not counting the day to day high price tag of gasoline. People are looking for viable means of transportation that is cost-effective and can move its way through traffic faster. In the Philippines, motorcycle was the answer to most people transportation needs. With the increasing number of a motorcycle rider in the Philippines safety is the utmost concern. Today technology plays a huge role on how this safety can be assured. We now see advances in connected devices. Devices can sense its surrounding through sensor attach to it. With this in mind, this study focuses on the development of a wearable device named Smart Motorcycle Helmet or simply Smart Helmet, whose main objective is to help motorcycle rider in times of emergency. Utilizing sensors such as alcohol level detector, crash/impact sensor, Internet connection thru 3G, accelerometer, Short Message Service (SMS) and cloud computing infrastructure connected to a Raspberry Pi Zero-W and integrating a separate Arduino board for the anti-theft tracking module is used to develop the propose Internet-of Things (IoT) device.

Using quantitative method and descriptive type research, the researchers validated the results from the inputs of the participant who tested the smart helmet during the alpha and beta testing process. Taking into account the ethical consideration of the volunteers, who will test the Smart Helmet. To ensure the reliability of the beta and alpha testing, ISO 25010 quality model was used for the assessment focusing on the device accuracy, efficiency and functionality. Based on the inputs and results gathered, the proposed Smart Helmet IoT device can be used as a tool in helping a motorcycle rider when an accident happens to inform the first-responder of the accident location and informing the family of the motorcycle rider.

KEYWORDS

Smart Helmet, Internet of Things, Sensors, Real-Time Crash Detection, Emergency Notification, Tracker, Anti-Theft System Cloud Based Technology

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AUTHORS

Dr. Marlon I. Tayag is a full-time Associate Professor at Holy Angel University and teaches Cyber Security subjects on Ethical Hacking and Forensic. He earned the degree of Doctor in Information Technology from St. Linus University in 2015 and is currently taking up Doctor of Philosophy in Computer Science at Technological Institute of the Philippines – Manila. Dr. Tayag is Cisco Certified Network Associate, 210-250 CCNA Understanding Cisco Cybersecurity Fundamentals and Fluke CCTTA – Certified Cabling Test Technician Associate. Microsoft Certified Professional and Microsoft Certified Educator.

Dr. Ma. Emmalyn A. V. Capuno is a currently the Dean of the Faculty of Information Technology of Future University Sudan with the academic rank of Associate Professor; a position she has been holding since 2009. She earned the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Information Technology Management from Colegio de San Juan Letran – Calamba, Philippines in 2005. Her teaching and research expertise includes Operating Systems, Knowledge Management, Business Intelligence and many more.

DATA MINING MODEL PERFORMANCE OF SALES PREDICTIVE ALGORITHMS BASED ON RAPIDMINER WORKFLOWS

Alessandro Massaro, Vincenzo Maritati, Angelo Galiano

**Dyrecta Lab, IT research Laboratory, via Vescovo Simplicio,
45, 70014 Conversano (BA), Italy**

ABSTRACT

By applying RapidMiner workflows has been processed a dataset originated from different data files, and containing information about the sales over three years of a large chain of retail stores. Subsequently, has been constructed a Deep Learning model performing a predictive algorithm suitable for sales forecasting. This model is based on artificial neural network –ANN- algorithm able to learn the model starting from sales historical data and by pre-processing the data. The best built model uses a multilayer eural network together with an “optimized operator” able to find automatically the best parameter setting of the implemented algorithm. In order to prove the best performing predictive model, other machine learning algorithms have been tested. The performance comparison has been performed between Support Vector Machine –SVM-, k- Nearest Neighbor k-NN-, Gradient Boosted Trees, Decision Trees, and Deep Learning algorithms. The comparison of the degree of correlation between real and predicted values, the verage absolute error and the relative average error proved that ANN exhibited the best performance. The Gradient Boosted Trees approach represents an alternative approach having the second best performance. The case of study has been developed within the framework of an industry project oriented on the integration of high performance data mining models able to predict sales using– ERP- and customer relationship management –CRM- tools.

KEYWORDS

RapidMiner, Neural Network, Deep Learning, Gradient Boosted Trees, Data Mining Performance, Sales Prediction.

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AUTHOR

Alessandro Massaro: Research & Development Chief of Dyrecta Lab s.r.l.

CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK BASED FEATURE EXTRACTION FOR IRIS RECOGNITION

Maram.G Alaslani¹ and Lamiaa A. Elrefaei^{1,2}

¹Computer Science Department, Faculty of Computing and Information Technology, King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

²Electrical Engineering Department, Faculty of Engineering at Shoubra, Benha University, Cairo, Egypt

ABSTRACT

Iris is a powerful tool for reliable human identification. It has the potential to identify individuals with a high degree of assurance. Extracting good features is the most significant step in the iris recognition system. In the past, different features have been used to implement iris recognition system. Most of them are depend on hand-crafted features designed by biometrics specialists. Due to the success of deep learning in computer vision problems, the features learned by the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) have gained much attention to be applied for iris recognition system. In this paper, we evaluate the extracted learned features from a pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (Alex-Net Model) followed by a multi-class Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm to perform classification. The performance of the proposed system is investigated when extracting features from the segmented iris image and from the normalized iris image. The proposed iris recognition system is tested on four public datasets IITD, iris databases CASIAIris-V1, CASIA-Iris-thousand and, CASIA-Iris- V3 Interval. The system achieved excellent results with the very high accuracy rate.

KEYWORDS

Biometrics, Iris, Recognition, Deep learning, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Feature extraction (FE).

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AUTHORS

Maram G. Alaslani Received her B.Sc. degree in Computer Science with Honors from King Abdulaziz University in 2010. She works as Teaching Assistant from 2011 to date at Faculty of Computers and Information Technology at King Abdulaziz University, Rabigh, Saudi Arabia. Now she is working in her Master Degree at King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. She has a research interest in image processing, pattern recognition, and neural network..

Lamiaa A. Elrefaei received her B.Sc. degree with honors in Electrical Engineering (Electronics and Telecommunications) in 1997, her M.Sc. in 2003 and Ph.D. in 2008 in Electrical Engineering (Electronics) from faculty of Engineering at Shoubra, Benha University, Egypt. She held a number of faculty positions at Benha University, as Teaching Assistant from 1998 to 2003, as an Assistant Lecturer from 2003 to 2008, and has been a lecturer from 2008 to date. She is currently an Associate Professor at the faculty of Computing and Information Technology, King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. Her research interests include computational intelligence, biometrics, multimedia security, wireless networks, and Nano networks. She is a senior member of IEEE.

QUERY OPTIMIZATION FOR BIG DATA ANALYTICS

Manoj Muniswamaiah, Tilak Agerwala and Charles Tappert

Seidenberg School of CSIS, Pace University, White Plains, New York

ABSTRACT

Organizations adopt different databases for big data which is huge in volume and have different data models. Querying big data is challenging yet crucial for any business. The data warehouses traditionally built with On-line Transaction Processing (OLTP) centric technologies must be modernized to scale to the ever-growing demand of data. With rapid change in requirements it is important to have near real time response from the big data gathered so that business decisions needed to address new challenges can be made in a timely manner. The main focus of our research is to improve the performance of query execution for big data.

KEYWORDS

Databases, Big data, Optimization, Analytical Query, Data Analysts and Data Scientists

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